

A Brief Look at Acute Intracerebral Hemorrhage

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Introduction

- Acute or spontaneous intracerebral hemorrhage (ICH) is a life-threatening state with high morbidity and mortality rates, accounting for roughly 10-15% of all strokes.
- ICH is a devastating form of stroke caused by the abrupt rupture of a blood vessel in the brain, causing a buildup of blood in the brain parenchyma.
- It is crucial to understand the etiology, pathophysiology, diagnosis strategies, and management approaches to improve patient outcomes.
- Despite advances in medical care, the management of ICH remains challenging, and its outcomes are often poor.
- This study delves into providing an overview of ICH with a review of current literature focusing on its etiology, pathophysiology, neuroimaging modalities, diagnosis, management approaches, and guiding treatment strategies.

Pathophysiology

The pathophysiology of ICH involves the rupture of small vessels within the brain parenchyma, leading to the accumulation of blood. The hematoma causes mass effect, leading to compression of surrounding brain tissue and subsequent ischemia and edema. Additionally, the release of blood products triggers an inflammatory response, further exacerbating brain injury. Although ICH is commonly considered a single-event disease, it has more recently been considered as a very dynamic condition with multiple phases, these being:

1. Initial extravasation of blood into the parenchyma
2. Subsequent bleeding around the clot causes expansion
3. Swelling or edema around the hematoma

In figure 2 we see an axial non-contrast CT scan of the brain that shows a hematoma.

Figure 2: Plain axial CT image reveals large, right parietal lobe hematoma causing mild compression of posterior part of the body of ipsilateral lateral ventricle; and diffuse white matter hypodensities

Diagnosis

- Diagnosis is based on clinical presentation, neuroimaging findings, and exclusion of other potential causes of ICH.
- Patients typically present with focal neurological deficits, such as hemiparesis or aphasia, depending on the location of the hemorrhage.
- Computerized tomography is essential for confirming the diagnosis and determining the extent of the hemorrhage.
- It is important to differentiate ICH from ischemic stroke, as the management strategies differ significantly.
- Figure 3 shows an algorithm with risk stratification to help in decision-making in ICH.
- Figure 4 illustrates the current American Heart Association guidelines for Primary ICH.

Literature Search Methodology

A focused search and systematic review of literature was conducted. Databases: PubMed, Scopus, CDC. Keywords: "acute", "intracerebral", "hemorrhage", "risk factors", "stroke" "management", "imaging". Collected data was analyzed for further evaluation and critical appraisal.

Figure 1. Cerebrovascular causes of intracerebral hemorrhage (ICH)

Etiology

ICH etiology is multifactorial, with numerous risk factors contributing to its development. Hypertension is the most common risk factor, accounting for about 70% of cases. There are some cerebrovascular risk factors as well as seen in Figure 1. Other factors may include illicit drug use (such as cocaine), and anticoagulant medication use. ICH can also occur secondary to trauma, tumor, or hemorrhagic transformation of an ischemic stroke.

Figure 3: Algorithm with risk stratification to help in decision-making on further imaging, and the diagnostic yield of intra-arterial digital subtraction angiography in ICH

Figure 4. American Heart Association Guideline overview for primary ICH

Management and Treatment

- The management of acute ICH involves both medical and surgical approaches.
- It is aimed at stabilizing the patient, minimizing further neurological injury, and preventing complications.
- Medical management focuses on stabilizing the patient, controlling blood pressure, and managing any underlying coagulopathy.
- Surgical interventions, such as hematoma evacuation or decompressive craniectomy, may be considered in select cases to relieve mass effect and improve outcomes.
- Rehabilitation plays a crucial role in the recovery phase, focusing on optimizing functional outcomes and quality of life.
- Figure 5 below shows an algorithm for acute intracerebral hemorrhage treatment.

Figure 5: Acute intracerebral hemorrhage treatment algorithm

Discussion and Conclusions

- Acute ICH represents a significant clinical challenge, requiring prompt diagnosis and aggressive management.
- Advances in neuroimaging and treatment strategies have improved outcomes, but the overall prognosis remains poor, especially in cases of large or deep-seated hematomas.
- In conclusion, acute intracerebral hemorrhage is a serious condition with high morbidity and mortality rates. More novel treatment approaches are needed to improve outcomes in patients with ICH.
- Continued research and advancements in treatment strategies will improve the prognosis of this devastating condition.

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Acknowledgements: This research was made possible by the generous contributions of the World Brain Mapping Foundation.